

Proposed Human Capital Management Strategy to Improve Elementary School Teachers' Competencies in Rahuning, North Sumatra, Indonesia (Case Study of SDIT Ar-Rahmah)

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ABSTRACT: The issue of low teacher competence in Indonesian schools outside of the big cities requires solutions from the outside and inside of the school. From within the organization, Human Capital Management (HCM) provides a beneficial framework for improving teachers' competence and overall school quality. This study aims to understand the low competency issues and the HCM system in Ar-Rahmah Rahuning Integrated Islamic Elementary School (SDIT Ar-Rahmah) and formulates competency development programs using Lifelong Learning (LLL) approach. In this mixed method research, a survey conducted on teachers' competency in SDIT Ar-Rahmah using the Teacher's Competence model outlined by the Director General of Teachers and Education Personnel in 2023 to evaluate four teacher's primary competence (pedagogic, personal, social, and professional competence), followed by a qualitative study on the HCM system, focusing on the competency development program. The study reveals that the average teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah indicate the need to improve pedagogic and social competence. Further, the HCM system in SDIT Ar-Rahmah lacks Professional Development and Performance Management for its teachers. The HCM system is highly reliant on the School Principal, which causes issues in developing Professional Development and Performance Management. A competency development program is formulated using Lifelong Learning approach to ensure continuous improvement throughout the teachers' employment. The program focuses on six key elements: 1) formal and nonformal education, 2) introspection and self-assessment, 3) self-motivated learning, 4) application of knowledge and skills, 5) evaluation and improvement steps, and 6) provision of facilities and tools that foster Lifelong Learning habits.

KEYWORDS: Competency development, Elementary school, Human capital management, Lifelong learning, Teacher's competence.

INTRODUCTION

The quality of educators is one of the determining factors that affect the quality of students, educational institutions, and ultimately a nation's human resources. In elementary education, teachers are an integral part of the student's development. However, teacher's competence is indeed one of the prevalent issues in Indonesia. According to The Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology (Kemendikbudristek), the results of national Teachers Competence Test or *Uji Kompetensi Guru* (UKG) in 2022 reveals the national average score for teachers at all levels (SD, SMP, SMA & SMK), including pedagogical and professional competence, that is at 54.05 which is below the passing standard of 55 (Kementerian Pendidikan, Kebudayaan, Riset dan Teknologi, 2019). The national average score for elementary school level is 52.01, for pedagogical competence is 50.43 and for professional competence is 55.46 (Kementerian Pendidikan, Kebudayaan, Riset dan Teknologi, 2019). Indeed, 60.58% regions in Indonesia show an average score below the passing standard of 55, whereas the region with an average score of 55 or above is 39.42%. This indicates that the teachers' competencies are still low, with teachers in 60.58% of the regions in Indonesia still struggling to meet the passing standard of UKG. The issues call for solutions both from the outside, such as governmental programs, and from the inside of the educational institution, namely through human capital management (HCM) practices. Human capital management is also a key factor in providing a system that ensures an organization's high quality of output. However, HR practices in schools are often managed poorly based on convenience, imitation of previous practices, contract constraints, and unclear administrative systems (Campbell, DeArmond & Schumwinger, 2004, cited in Odden, 2011, p.34). Yet, research shows that the human capital management system plays a pivotal role in improving the quality of teachers through careful planning, implementation of training programs, and periodic evaluations (Sholeh et al., 2021). Indeed, human capital management systems shall be focused on improving teacher's

competencies to contribute to student achievement (Heneman & Milanowski, 2007, cited in Odden, 2011: 34). Clearly human capital management is an element that should be focused on when formulating strategy to improve teachers' competence.

I. Business Issue

Ar-Rahmah Rahuning Integrated Islamic Elementary School (SDIT Ar-Rahmah) is an elementary school in Rahuning district, Asahan Regency, North Sumatra. The elementary school was established in 2016 and managed under the Ar-Rahmah Educational Foundation (YP Ar-Rahmah). SDIT Ar-Rahmah integrates Islamic teaching in its curriculum in addition to the National 2013 Curriculum from The Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology (Kemendikbudristek), making it one of its advantages compared to other elementary schools in Asahan regency. SDIT Ar-Rahmah currently faces the challenge of teachers' competence.

A. Lack of Teachers Qualifications

Teacher's qualification reflects the formal education that a teacher has received, which have a significant impact on their competence level. In SDIT Ar-Rahmah, less than half of the teachers holds a bachelor's degree in education, with only four teachers holding said degree. Additionally, none of the teachers are certified, indicating a lack of formal education and training in teaching elementary students. Most teachers also have limited experience teaching at elementary level, with only three teachers classified as experienced based on the definition of Freeman (2001, cited in Shohani, 2015). Teacher's experience is positively associated with greater student achievements and benefits for colleagues (Podolsky, Kini & Darling-Hammond, 2019). The more experience teachers accumulate in the same grade, subjects, or district, the more likely the students to perform better on several measures of success (Podolsky, Kini & Darling-Hammond, 2019). Thus, teachers' experience is also an integral part of effective teaching, which makes it an essential indicator of a teacher's qualifications. Teachers' competence and qualifications are considered for school accreditation by the National Accreditation Board for Schools and Madrasahs (BAN-SM), and the Teacher and Educational Staff Standard component receives the lowest points in SDIT Ar-Rahmah's accreditation scores, highlighting the need for improvements in teacher competence.

Figure 1. SDIT Ar-Rahmah Teachers Last Education

Figure 2. SDIT Ar-Rahmah's Teachers Teaching Experience

B. Lack of Creativity and Innovation in Teaching Methods

Teachers’ creativity in developing innovative teaching methods is crucial when dealing with elementary students to prevent boredom and lack of focus. According to Monawati & Fauzi (2018, p.33) teachers’ creativity in developing their teaching methods and in the use of media, along with attentiveness to students’ potential, are strongly influential towards students’ achievement. Thus, a creative and innovative teaching method is indispensable to a successful teaching process. However, most teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah rarely innovate their methods, with only one teacher regularly do so through ice breaking activities. The lack of initiative in fostering enthusiasm among students is a concern. Moreover, with the implementation of the new Merdeka Belajar curriculum, emphasizing student-centred and project-based learning, the need for teacher’s innovation and creativity has become more urgent, requiring strong pedagogic and professional skills to ensure effective student engagement (Anggraena et al., 2022; Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023). Clearly, the need for teachers’ initiative for innovation and creativity is becoming significantly more pressing with the adoption of Merdeka Belajar curriculum.

C. Lack of Human Capital Management Strategy for Competency Development

In addition to teachers’ competence, evidence shows that HCM issues contribute to challenges with teachers competence. The issues mainly revolve around the lack of strategic approach to competency development and alignment of human resource practices. To achieve accreditation improvement, a competency development strategy is crucial for ensuring high-quality output from teachers. However, the school currently has limited professional training and development programs, with the Program Pendidikan Guru (PPG) certification being the primary option. The certification aims to improve teachers competencies and welfare, yet, many teachers are unable to participate due to administrative requirements. It also appears that competency development is not a priority in the HCM system as there is no internal training program being planned. Despite the guidance from the BoD members and Founders to develop training programs, the School Principal did not make it a priority to do so. According to his testimony, the School Principal is overwhelmed with his workload as the school doubles its capacity for the new 2023/2023 Academic Year (Z. Marpaung, personal communication, July 1, 2023). Other teachers are also adjusting to the increased workload and expanded school capacity. Thus, delaying the formulation and planning for the competency development program. Figure 1.8 shows the analysis of this issue using the Five Why’s framework. From the analysis, the root cause is a lack of competence in human capital management.

Figure 2. Five Why’s Analysis

LITERATURE REVIEW

I. Competence

Competence and competence management has shown growing significance in the field of psychology and human resource management. Particularly in the 1990s when competency became the innovative approach to development of human resource studies and practices (Collin & Holden, 1997, cited in Moore, Cheng & Dainty, 2002, p.314). McClelland (1973) brought a substantive

impact in the field when he initiated an investigation for more effective tools to predict individuals job performance. He stresses that competency should also be given more account in predicting one's performance on a specific job, rather than intelligence alone (McClelland, 1973). He also suggests that one's competencies should be considered and measured against the specific skills that are necessary for a certain job as well as life skills that are more generally useful such as communication skills, leadership, and interpersonal skills (McClelland, 1973, p.9-10). Further, competence is defined as a person's basic characteristics that can be measured to indicate one's performance for a specific task (Spencer & Spencer, 1993, p.4). Wong (2020, p.100) defines competency as a "set of observable and measurable attributes or success factors required for individuals for effective work performance". This definition is aligned with McClelland's idea of competence as described as a set of prerequisites that an individual shall have to perform a task well. In addition, competency as a behavioral quality covers different attributes of an individual including knowledge, skills, self-concept and values, personal traits and motives (Spencer & Spencer, 1993). Sedarmayanti, Komariah, Kurniady and Zafar (2020, p.95) further concluded that competence contains three variables, that are knowledge, skill, and attitude. Some attributes or variables of competence are easier to measure than others, particularly knowledge and skills, whereas attitudes, self-concept, personal traits, and motives are harder to observe and measure. Nonetheless, all variables play an essential role in measuring one's competence and predicting future job performance.

Studies have also pointed out the increasing importance of competence, particularly in identifying useful skills for a certain occupation and in designing programs to develop certain competencies by employers. The five dimension of professional competence framework by Cheetham and Chivers (1996, cited in Le Deist & Winterton, 2005) is used to analyze the skills required for managers and professionals in the UK along with some modifications to determine the required skills (Le Deist & Winterton, 2005, p.36). It also helps employers and HR practitioners to understand better the required skill sets to perform a certain task and identify those competencies in their future employees. Other competence models can assist in improving synergy between education and work provision as well as cultivating professional competence through educational programs, namely formal education, and experiential learning (Le Deist and Winterton, 2005). Thus, competence models can help design training programs according to individual and organization needs.

II. Teacher's Competence

In Indonesia, teaching is a profession that holds a strategic position in building a nation's human resources. Research shows that teachers' competencies have a positive and significant influence on their teaching performance (Siri et al., 2020). More importantly, teachers' competencies also have a positive impact towards student's motivation and learning outcomes (Saptono & Aylina, 2022). Consequently, teaching is one of the occupations that are highly regulated by the Indonesian government, including their competences. In fact, the government regulates four major competences that one shall possess to become a competent teacher. According to the Regulation of the Director General of Teachers and Education Personnel Number 2626/B/HK.04.01/2023 about Teachers Competence Model, the four competences include:

1) Pedagogical Competence

Pedagogical competence is an ability that is closely related to the characteristics of students as seen from many perspectives such as moral, emotional, and intellectual. As students have varied personalities, traits, and interests, a teacher must be able to master learning theory and learning principles and apply it to the observed behaviour of their students accordingly. In terms of curriculum implementation, a teacher shall be able to create a curriculum at the level of each educational unit and adapt it to local demands. Teachers shall be able to maximize students' ability to actualize their abilities in class, as well as carry out assessment activities on the learning activities completed. The following are the abilities that are included in the pedagogical competence of a teacher: 1) mastery of students' physical, moral, social, cultural, emotional, and intellectual traits, 2) knowledge of learning theory and concepts of educational learning, 3) capable of developing courses in the field of development enabled, 4) planning and developing educational activities, 5) make use of information technology and communication to benefit the organization of educational development activities, 6) facilitate the growth of students potential, 7) communicate with students in an effective, compassionate, and respectful manner, 8) assess and evaluate learning processes and outcomes, leveraging assessment and evaluation results for learning benefit, 9) take reflective steps to improve learning quality. (Direktorat Tenaga Kependidikan, 2008; Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023).

2) Personal competence

Personal competence is the ability to be a role model for kids while having a strong personality that is noble, smart, and authoritative. The performance of duties as a teacher must be accompanied by a sense of pride in the responsibility entrusted to him of preparing quality future generations of the nation. In other words, a teacher must be passionate about norms, morality, aesthetics, and knowledge, which will eventually affect students' ethical behavior as people and members of society. Teachers must be able to educate their students on self-discipline, how to read, how to enjoy books, how to respect time, how to study, how to comply with rules/regulations, and how to act. All of this will be effective if the teacher is disciplined in carrying out his duties and commitments. Teachers must possess abilities related to personality stability and integrity. The following are competencies included in personal competence: 1) act in line with Indonesian religious, legal, social, and national cultural norms, 2) present oneself as an honest, noble individual who serves as a role model for students and society, 3) present oneself as a steady, stable, mature, intelligent, and authoritative individual, 4) show a strong work ethic, a sense of duty, pride in being a teacher, and confidence, 5) uphold the teaching profession's code of ethics. (Direktorat Tenaga Kependidikan, 2008; Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023)

3) Social Competence

Social competence, defined as teachers' capacity to communicate and engage effectively and efficiently with students, fellow teachers, students' parents/guardians, and the surrounding community. Teachers are role models in the eyes of society and students, and they are role models in everyday life. Teachers must have interpersonal skills to implement an effective learning process. With this skill, the school's contact with the community will automatically operate smoothly, so that if there is a need with the students' parents, the teachers will not go into difficulty. The ability of the instructor to communicate, collaborate, get along sympathetically, and have a nice soul are examples of social skills. The following are teacher social competence requirements that must be met: 1) act objectively and without discrimination based on gender, religion, race, physical condition, family background, or socioeconomic status, 2) communicate effectively, empathically, and pleasantly with colleagues, educational personnel, parents, and members of the community, 3) adapt in place of duty within the Republic of Indonesia's socio-culturally diverse area, 4) oral and written communication with the professional community as well as other professions. (Direktorat Tenaga Kependidikan, 2008; Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023)

4) Professional competence

Professional competence, defined as broad and deep subject matter expertise. Professional competence is the skill teachers must have to organize and implement the learning process to attain learning objectives, hence teachers must be able to deliver instructional material. Teachers must also be adaptable to change and swiftly acquire the most up-to-date information to offer most updated learning materials (Direktorat Tenaga Kependidikan, 2008; Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023).

III. Human Capital Management

Human capital management (HCM) emerges as a new approach to people management in response to the shortcomings of Personnel Management and Human resource management (HRM) practices. While traditional practices view employees as liability or resource to be managed for the organization's benefits, HCM recognizes employees as valuable assets that need to be effectively aligned with the organization's goals. This shift in paradigm addresses the challenges posed by the increasing number of highly educated and independent employees, necessitating a cooperative approach beyond authority and compensation alone. HCM focuses on building and maintaining alignment between individuals and organisations to foster commitment, dedication and loyalty, ultimately enhancing employee productivity (van Marrewijk & Timmers, 2003).

HCM, as defined by Ingham (2007) is a method to leverage value from people for business success and competitive advantage. It views human capital as an investment that can appreciate overtime if properly managed, emphasizing the importance of creating value for employees to enhance organizational value. It also emphasizes the importance of measurement which entails knowledge, complexity, best fit, and intangibility in the process (Ingham, 2007). HCM optimizes employee capacity and engagement to produce valuable intangible capabilities that align with long-term business strategy. In its implementation, HCM practices focus on finding, developing, compensating, and retaining high-quality talents with the right knowledge and skills to execute organizational improvement strategies (Odden, 2011).

IV. Human Capital Management in Education

The role of human resource management in education has undergone a paradigm change. Previously, it was more centralized, focusing on managing existing human resources. However, the current paradigm emphasizes systematic development and empowerment programs to enable teachers and educational staff to grow professionally. Human resource management in education now includes both operational and managerial actions, aiming to optimize personal and collective capacity to achieve organizational objectives, aligning with the principles of HCM. In educational institutions, HCM practices differ from those in commercial organizations. The management goals in education range from personal objectives, ensuring equitable opportunities and fostering individual motivation, to functional objectives, supporting teachers' effective performance. Organizational objectives focus on effectiveness and growth, while societal objectives address societal demands and prepare younger generations to face future challenges for the nation's benefit (Ulfatin & Triwiyanto, 2016).

HCM practices in educational institutions differ from commercial organizations. According to Ulfatin and Triwijyanto (2016), human resource management in education optimizes resources to contribute meaningfully to educational goals for individuals, schools, and society. Understanding organizational objectives is crucial for achieving optimum performance. They outline four management goals for educational institutions, ranging from personal objectives, offering equitable opportunities, and fostering motivation, to societal objectives, fulfilling societal demands and preparing younger generations for future challenges to benefit the nation (Ulfatin & Triwiyanto, 2016). Clearly, HCM in education differs from commercial organizations as it prioritizes improving educator and staff performance while creating a harmonious learning environment for the benefit of students, parents, and society. It is crucial to empower educators to enhance their abilities and positively impact educational quality. According to Suryana (2013, p.196), teachers' understanding of learning methodologies, attitudes, and motivation have a direct effect on student learning results. Other study has demonstrated that enhancing teacher competency has a favorable influence on performance (Destiana et al, 2012 quoted in Agung & Capnary 2018, p.3), which in turn benefits student learning outcomes (Samuel et al, 2013 cited in Agung & Capnary 2018, p.3). Odden (2011) outlines three essential program areas for a well-run HCM system in education: talent acquisition, talent development and motivation, and talent retention, all of which are interrelated processes. Qualified educators and educational personnel are vital for effective human resource management in education. Empowering educators and focusing on student learning methodologies, attitudes, and motivation can lead to improved student learning outcomes. Thus, developing teacher competency is essential for achieving management objectives and positive social impact.

V. Competency Development

Competency development is an integral component in HCM strategy in order to gain competitive advantage on organisation level. Organisations benefit from competent employees through numerous HR process, including a robust recruitment and selection and well-developed training programs and appraisal system (Bach, 2001, cited in Alsabbah & Ibrahim, 2014). Human resource activities can positively influence organisational performance by developing competent employees (Ghebreorgis & Karsten, 2007). Thus, it is essential to design human resource processes to complement the improvement of employee's competency (Neal & Griffin, 1999; Fey et al., 2000; Park et al., 2003). In this sense, competency development is not just a goal, but rather, a means to achieve organisational success.

Indonesian government regulations (Article 20 of Law No. 14 of 2005) mandate that teachers continuously enhance their academic credentials and competencies to keep up with advancements in science, technology, and art. Indeed, teacher competence significantly influences learning success, educational quality, and the overall learning experience Spencer and Spencer (1993, p.7). Low teacher competence hampers the learning process, especially for primary school students with lower self-regulation. Conversely, teachers with high cognitive levels demonstrate abstract thinking, creativity, and better relationships with students and colleagues (Imron, 1995). Moreover, the growth of teacher competence can positively impact school evaluations, with competent teachers providing quality feedback on the learning process and school management. It is essential for schools and affiliated organizations to support teacher competency development through training actively and providing necessary facilities, as the environment plays a vital role in shaping individual competency (Uno, 2009).

Additionally, research suggests the effectiveness of competency development programs by schools in improving teachers' competence. Antariksa (2017) explores the human resource management in Islamic elementary school SDIT Insan Permata in Malang and discovers the effectiveness of the internal and external trainings in its competency development program. The program

included induction and monthly training, external trainings through Integrated Islamic School Network (JSIT) East Java and Malang, and certification training via Teacher Professional Education and Training (PLPG) for professional certification. This diverse approach aligns with Maisyaroh's (2014) human resource development strategy, which emphasizes various education methods, individual consultations, organizational visits, workshops, internships, and mentorship. As a result, the teachers in SDIT Insan Permata were able to expand their knowledge and learn from the capabilities of teachers in other schools. Musfah (2011, p.69) suggests avoiding solely focusing on technical skills. Instead, a comprehensive approach should consider the teacher's knowledge, experience, and trust, in addition to technical skills. Musfah (2011, p.69) highlights two key features of a successful program: support and feedback from school leaders, management, and senior staff to build trust, and tailoring the training program to teachers' needs and abilities for easier implementation and evaluation (Musfah, 2011; Seyfarth 2002; Siagian, 2003).

VI. Lifelong Learning

Lifelong Learning (LLL) refers to ongoing activities individuals engage in to enhance their knowledge, skills, and competence for personal, social, or work-related reasons (Field, 2001). It involves formal and informal education, providing second chances to update competencies and pursue advanced education. An ideal LLL framework allows for diverse learning settings, occupations, locations, and nations to maximize individual growth and competences (Harvey, 2004). To apply LLL effectively, education and vocational training should be integrated into key elements of education, youth, employment, and research. Learners must adopt a proactive approach, becoming active researchers and contributors to knowledge construction (Fischer & Ostwald, 2002). For teachers, LLL is crucial for continuous development and adapting to evolving times. Teacher education should instill a learning spirit to prepare competent teachers. Schools must actively support teachers in pursuing further education and training to foster a love for learning (Musfah, 2011, p.118).

To promote Lifelong Learning (LLL), education and vocational training should be integrated into key elements of education, youth, employment, and research. Learners must adopt a proactive approach, becoming active researchers and contributors to knowledge construction. Learners should also be able to utilise facilities in the learning process, while also actively contributing to the facilities by sharing their expertise and assisting other learners. (Fischer & Ostwald, 2002) LLL is a suitable method for developing teachers' competence as it requires continuous learning throughout their careers. Teacher education should instill a learning spirit to prepare competent teachers. Schools must actively support teachers in pursuing further education and training to foster a love for learning (Musfah, 2011).

In his research, Musfah (2011) found that Madania School in Bogor effectively uses a Lifelong Learning (LLL) approach to enhance teachers' competencies. New teachers undergo a four-month training program (PGM) combining theory and practice, and all teachers undergo continuous training and evaluation throughout their careers. They are also supported by various learning resources, seminars, and workshops to encourage independent learning. Evaluation occurs periodically from four layers of evaluators, namely their own self-reflection, observation from School Principal, evaluation from colleagues on the teachers' interactions with Madania's environment (including students, other teachers, parents, and more), and finally performance evaluation from students (Musfah, 2011, p. 138). The school forms a team to design and execute the trainings, involving various departments and senior teachers. Existing teachers are encouraged to engage in continuous learning and join PGM as needed. The implementation of LLL has operational implications, including the need for competent staff, well-managed learning materials, flexibility and adequate facilities, and excellent learning tools. The program has positive impacts on all aspects of teacher competence, improving not only their teaching but also fostering positive habits and improving their quality of life.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

I. Data Collection Methods

This research is using a mixed method for the data collection. Indeed, the use of multiple methods is suggested for research in business and management to overcome the limitations of employing a single method, as well as to allow for a more comprehensive approach to data collecting, analysis, and interpretation (Bryman, 2006, cited in Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016, p.164). In this study, the data collection method is designed to utilise mixed method, combining the use of quantitative data and by qualitative data. The data collection process consisted of three stages as follows:

- 1) First, to assess the current competence of SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers, quantitative data collection via a questionnaire will be utilized. For comprehensive evaluation, it will employ a 270-degree approach, involving supervisor, peer, and self-evaluations (Noe et al., 2021, p.367). The school principal will evaluate all 12 teachers, while peers will assess each other based on collaboration frequency and subject/class similarities. Self-evaluation will provide additional insights into teachers' perceptions of their own competence. This comprehensive method enhances evaluation accuracy.
- 2) Second, individual semi-structured interviews will be conducted with the School Principal and staff in charge of the HCM process to describe the current HCM system in the organisation. The interviewees include School Principal, Administrative officer, as well as the Head of YP Ar-Rahmah.
- 3) Third, primary data will be analysed and combined with secondary data from academic sources to explore and formulate the HCM strategy that can improve the current teachers competence.

A. Survey Design

To understand the current competence of the teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah, a survey will be conducted using a questionnaire. The Regulation of the Director General of Teachers and Education Personnel Number 2626/B/HK.04.01/2023 about Teachers Competence Model (Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023) outlines the required competence that elementary school teachers shall possess. The competences outlined will be used as the basis for the survey. Further, each teacher will have 3 evaluations: from one peer, supervisor (School Principal), and self-evaluation. Finally, the competence is measured using a five categories likert scale rating based on the explanation of competency level mastery as cited in the Teachers Competence Model. For self-evaluation, the survey questions and likert scale rating will also be adjusted accordingly.

B. Semi-structured Interview Design

The semi-structured interview is aimed to explain the existing HCM system implemented in the organization as well as the current capabilities and limitations faced by the school. Thus, provides a wider understanding on the underlying viewpoint that drives the arrangement of the existing system. The interview also seeks to discover the attitude towards HCM of the people who are able to affect the system and the reasoning for the system currently implemented. Furthermore, the interview will be conducted with 3 sources, including The interviewees include School Principal, Administrative officer, as well as the Head of YP Ar-Rahmah.

II. Data Analysis Methods

A. Quantitative Data

The quantitative data collected from the questionnaire will be tested for its validity and reliability. Afterwards, the data will be combined to get an overall of the sub-competences to get a better understanding of each individual competence and the overall competence of SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers. In the analysis, the score will be calculated using weighted average to minimise the impact of inflated assessments on self-evaluations. Indeed, self-evaluations for personal traits, behaviour and overall performance tend to be lenient compared other source of evaluations as employees tend to inflate their own ratings to avoid undesirable consequences Heidemeier & Moser, 2008, cited in Noe et al., 2021, p. 369). To reduce the impact and ensure the data is reflective of the actual competence of the teacher, lower weight will be given for the self-evaluation ratings. The weight is distributed as follows: 40% for Supervisor Evaluation, 40% for Peer Evaluation and 20% for Self-Evaluation. The total score is calculated by multiplying the weight of each factor with its rating and then adding the individual scores to get total points.

B. Qualitative Data

A particular method for analyzing qualitative data is qualitative Thematic Narrative Analysis. Thematic Narrative Analysis is a method for analyzing a single narrative or a group of connected narratives. It focuses on the chronology of events and contextual background of the identified topics to generate a rich and comprehensive analysis. Multiple narratives are examined individually in this approach before comparing and contrasting findings across them. (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016, p.603). This study will utilise Thematic Narrative Analysis to analyse the qualitative data from the interview. The individual narrative will be given its own analysis. The results will then be compiled to achieve an overall understanding on the HCM system in SDIT Ar-Rahmah.

FINDINGS & DISCUSSIONS

I. Quantitative Data Analysis

A. Validity Test

This research uses Pearson’s Correlation. The results of the r calculations will be compared to the r table where DF = N-2 5%. If r count > r table, then the question is valid. Table 1 shows the results. The r count of all the sub-competence is greater than r-table (0.3291) which indicates that all the items in the competence evaluation are valid.

B. Reliability Test

The consistency with which a measurement process, experiment, or test produces the same result after several tries is referred to as reliability. The degree of agreement between two or more coders or raters is known as interrater reliability. Interrater reliability discusses how consistently a rating method is applied. The key in reliability testing is the agreement among independent observers or raters. Generally, the more raters agree on the data they generate, the more reliable the data (Hayes & Krippendorff, 2007, p.78). In this research, there are three raters of teachers’ competencies, which include self, supervisor, and peer. Thus, in testing for reliability, the Krippendorff’s alpha is utilised in this paper as it allows for calculating reliability of three raters or more The Krippendorff’s alpha is analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics. Table 2 shows the results of reliability test on the 12 teachers evaluated by three raters. The results of reliability tests show a variety of Krippendorff’s alpha. The result of three teachers’ competence evaluation shows good inter-rater agreement. This means that the data on teacher 005, teacher 009 and teacher 011 shows is reliable. There is a good level agreement between the three raters on the evaluated competence. The remaining Krippendorff’s alpha teachers’ competencies evaluation score shows a low inter-rater agreement (teacher 002, teacher 003, teacher 010, teacher 012) and very low inter-rater agreement (teacher 001, teacher 004, teacher 006-008). This means that there are little agreement on the score given by three raters, which also shows low reliability of the data.

Table 1. Validity Test Results

Competence	r Calculations	Interpretation		
Pedagogic Competence	1.1.1	0,35	Valid	
	1.1.2	0,349	Valid	
	1.1.3	0,39	Valid	
	1.2.1	0,37	Valid	
	1.2.2	0,33	Valid	
	1.2.3	0,376	Valid	
	1.2.4	0,415	Valid	
	1.2.5	0,411	Valid	
	1.3.1	0,498	Valid	
	1.3.2	0,419	Valid	
	1.3.3	0,454	Valid	
	1.3.4	0,415	Valid	
	1.3.5	0,447	Valid	
	So Personal Competence	2.1.1	0,61	Valid
		2.1.2	0,566	Valid
2.1.3		0,54	Valid	
2.2.1		0,553	Valid	
2.2.2		0,553	Valid	
2.2.3		0,585	Valid	
2.3.1		0,54	Valid	
2.3.2		0,422	Valid	
2.3.3		0,48	Valid	
3.1.1	0,638	Valid		

Professional Competence	3.1.2	0,543	Valid
	3.1.3	0,635	Valid
	3.2.1	0,378	Valid
	3.2.2	0,361	Valid
	3.3.1	0,416	Valid
	3.3.2	0,414	Valid
	4.1.1	0,367	Valid
	4.1.2	0,545	Valid
	4.1.3	0,412	Valid
	4.2.1	0,635	Valid
	4.2.2	0,646	Valid
	4.2.3	0,646	Valid
4.2.4	0,548	Valid	
4.2.5	0,495	Valid	
4.3.1	0,614	Valid	
4.3.2	0,766	Valid	
4.3.3	0,476	Valid	
4.3.4	0,564	Valid	

Table 2. Reliability Test Results

Teacher's Code	Krippendorf's Alpha	Interpretation
001	0,5997	Very low inter-rater reliability
002	0,7342	Low inter-rater reliability
003	0,7927	Low inter-rater reliability
004	0,5426	Very low inter-rater reliability
005	0,869	Good inter-rater reliability
006	0,5667	Very low inter-rater reliability
007	0,5785	Very low inter-rater reliability
008	0,1969	Very low inter-rater reliability
009	0,8803	Good inter-rater reliability
010	0,7993	Low inter-rater reliability
011	0,8225	Good inter-rater reliability
012	0,7209	Low inter-rater reliability

C. Teachers' Competency Survey Findings

Table 4.4 shows the average competence score of all the teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah, which amounts to 12 teachers in total. The total average competence score of SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers is 3,57 out of 5. Professional competence has the highest average score of 4,03 out of 5, followed by personal competence with an average score of 3,89. Both professional and personal competence are shown to be more superior suit of SDIT Ar-Rahmah's teachers as the two competences are above the total average competence score (3,57). Pedagogic competence is averaged at 3,30 out of 5 and social competence has the lowest score that is at 3,06 out of 5. Both pedagogic and social competence shows lower score than the total average competence score that is at 3,57. A more detailed analyses on each competence will be provided below.

1) Pedagogic Competence

Pedagogic competence consists of 3 indicators and 13 sub-indicators. For indicator **1.1 A safe and comfortable learning environment for students**, SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers averaged at 3,13 overall. This score is below the total average competence

score that is at 3,57. According to the Operational Framework of Teachers Competence Model (Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023), the average score for this indicator is included in the level 3 competence which indicates that the average teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah are able to evaluate the implementation strategy for a safe and comfortable learning environment for students and design improvements to the strategy. For indicator **1.2 Effective student-centred learning**, SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers averaged at 3,23 overall. This score is below the total average competence score that is at 3,57. According to the Operational Framework of Teachers Competence Model (Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023), the average score for this indicator is included in the level 3 competence which indicates that the average teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah can evaluate the strategy for effective student-centred learning and design improvements to the strategy. It is important to note that two out of five sub-indicators in this competence does not reach the score 3, that is at 2,92 for sub-indicator **1.2.2 Design learning that is relevant to the circumstances around the school by involving students** and 2,69 for sub-indicator **1.2.3. Selection and use of learning resources suitable for learning purposes**. The score reflects level 2 competency level, which indicates that the average teacher are designing learning that is relevant and involving the students (sub-indicator 1.2.2) and selecting and utilising the right learning sources that suits the learning outcomes (sub-indicator 1.2.3). For indicator **1.3 Student-centred assessment, feedback, and reporting** SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers averaged at 3,55 overall. This score is slightly below the total average competence score that is at 3,57. According to the Operational Framework of Teachers Competence Model (Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023), the average score for this indicator is included in the level 3 competence which indicates that the average teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah can evaluate student-centred assessment, feedback and reporting and design improvement.

2) Personal Competence

Personal competence consists of 3 indicators and 9 sub-indicators. For indicator **2.1 Moral, emotional, and spiritual maturity to behave according to the teacher's code of ethics**, SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers averaged at 3,96 overall. This score is above the total average competence score that is at 3,57. According to the Operational Framework of Teachers Competence Model (Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023), the average score for this indicator is included in the level 3 competence which indicates that the average teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah are able to evaluate behavior that reflects moral, emotional, and spiritual maturity to behave in accordance with the teacher's code of ethics and plan improvements. For indicator **2.2 Self-development through the habit of reflection**, SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers averaged at 3,74 overall. This score is above the total average competence score that is at 3,57. According to the Operational Framework of Teachers Competence Model (Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023), the average score for this indicator is included in the level 3 competence which indicates that the average teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah can evaluate the application of self-development through reflection habits and design improvements. For indicator **2.3 Students-centric orientation**, SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers averaged at 3,97 overall. This score is above the total average competence score that is at 3,57. According to the Operational Framework of Teachers Competence Model (Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023), the average score for this indicator is included in the level 3 competence which indicates that the average teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah can evaluate habits in placing students as the center of learning and designing improvements.

3) Social Competence

Social competence consists of 3 indicators and 7 sub-indicators. For indicator **3.1 Collaboration for improved learning**, SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers averaged at 3,52 overall. This score is slightly below the total average competence score that is at 3,57. According to the Operational Framework of Teachers Competence Model (Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023), the average score for this indicator is included in the level 3 competence which indicates that the average teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah can evaluate collaborative strategies to improve the quality of learning and design improvements. For indicator **3.2 Parent/guardian and community involvement in learning**, SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers averaged at 3,57 overall. This score is the same as total average competence score that is at 3,57. According to the Operational Framework of Teachers Competence Model (Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023), the average score for this indicator is included in the level 3 competence which indicates that the average teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah can evaluate parent/guardian and community involvement in learning and design more effective engagement strategies. For indicator **3.3 Engagement in the organization of professions and broader networks for improved learning**, SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers averaged at 2,08 overall. This score is below the total average competence score that is at 3,57. According to the Operational Framework of Teachers Competence Model (Direktorat Jenderal

Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023), the average score for this indicator is included in the level 2 competence which indicates that the average teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah can play a role in professional organizations and wider networks to improve the quality of student learning.

4) Professional Competence

Professional competence consists of 3 indicators and 12 sub-indicators. For indicator **4.1 Knowledge of learning content and how to teach it**, SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers averaged at 4,12 overall. This score is above the total average competence score that is at 3,57. According to the Operational Framework of Teachers Competence Model (Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023), the average score for this indicator is included in the level 4 competence which indicates that the average teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah can collaborate with colleagues regarding knowledge of learning content and how to teach it. For indicator **4.2 Characteristics and learning methods of students**, SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers averaged at 3,86 overall. This score is above the total average competence score that is at 3,57. According to the Operational Framework of Teachers Competence Model (Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023), the average score for this indicator is included in the level 3 competence which indicates that the average teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah are able to evaluate knowledge in determining the characteristics that will affect the way students learn and plan improvements. For indicator **4.3 Curriculum and how to use it**, SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers averaged at 3,99 overall. This score is above the total average competence score that is at 3,57. According to the Operational Framework of Teachers Competence Model (Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2023), the average score for this indicator is included in the level 3 competence which indicates that the average teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah are able to evaluate knowledge of curriculum components and how to use them to design instructional designs and plan improvements.

Table 3. Teachers' Competencies Survey Results

Elementary Teachers Competency Standard		Average Score	Note
1. Pedagogic Competence		3,30	Below Average
1.1	A safe and comfortable learning environment for students	3,13	Below Average
	1.1.1. Managing difficult student behavior	3,08	Below Average
	1.1.2. Classroom management to student-centric learning	3,14	Below Average
	1.1.3. A sense of safety and comfort in the learning process	3,17	Below Average
1.2	Effective student-centred learning	3,23	Below Average
	1.2.1. Structured and sequential learning design to learning goals	3,50	Below Average
	1.2.2. Learning design that is relevant to the circumstances around the school by involving students	2,92	Below Average
	1.2.3. Selection and use of learning resources suitable for learning purposes	2,69	Below Average
	1.2.4. Learning instruction that includes strategies and communication to cultivate the interests and critical minds of the students	3,51	Below Average
	1.2.5. Adaptive use of information and communication technology (ICT) in learning	3,54	Below Average
1.3	Student-centred assessment, feedback, and reporting	3,55	Below Average
	1.3.1. A student-centric assessment design	3,42	Below Average
	1.3.2. Implementation of a student-centred assessment	3,42	Below Average
	1.3.3. Feedback to the student about his studies	3,41	Below Average
	1.3.4. Preparation of student achievement report	3,75	OK
	1.3.5. Communicate of student achievement report	3,76	OK
2. Personal Competence		3,89	OK
2.1	Moral, emotional, and spiritual readiness to behave in accordance with the teacher's code of ethics	3,96	OK
	2.1.1. The meaning, purpose, and view of the teacher's life based on moral principles and his belief in the One God	4,08	OK

	2.1.2. Emotional management in performing the role of educator	3,89	OK
	2.1.3. Application of teachers' code of ethics in work and learning	3,92	OK
2.2	Self-development through the habit of reflection	3,74	OK
	2.2.1 Reflection and planning of student-centred self-development needs	3,75	OK
	2.2.2. Adaptive methods of self-development to enhance student-centric learning	3,75	OK
	2.2.3. Application of self-development results to enhance student learning	3,72	OK
2.3	Students-centric orientation	3,97	OK
	2.3.1. Active and empathic interaction with students	3,98	OK
	2.3.2. Respect for the right of the student to perform the role of teacher	3,92	OK
	2.3.3. Concern for the safety and safety of students as individuals and groups	4,02	OK
3. Social Competence		3,06	Below Average
3.1	Collaboration for improved learning	3,52	Below Average
	3.1.1. Effective communication with school citizens that leads to improved learning	3,55	Below Average
	3.1.2. Organization of tasks with peers for improved learning	3,47	Below Average
	3.1.3. Initiatives contribute to achieving common goals in improving learning	3,53	Below Average
3.2	Parent/parent and community involvement in learning	3,57	Below Average
	3.2.1. Parental support in support of home-centric pupil learning	3,55	Below Average
	3.2.2. Connecting the knowledge, expertise, and perspectives of parents and society in participatory-centric learning	3,58	OK
3.3	Engagement in the organization of professions and broader networks for improved learning	2,08	Below Average
	3.3.1. Participate in diverse roles for learning problem solving in the broader professional organization and networking.	2,08	Below Average
	3.3.2. Sharing good practices and work for improving learning centred on the student in the broader organizations and networks.	2,08	Below Average
4. Professional Competence		4,03	OK
4.1	Knowledge of learning content and how to teach it	4,12	OK
	4.1.1. Structure and flow of knowledge of a field of science relevant to learning.	4,23	OK
	4.1.2. Identify knowledge content that is relevant to achieving learning goals.	3,99	OK
	4.1.3. Organization of knowledge content relevant to learning	4,15	OK
4.2	Characteristics and learning methods of students	3,86	OK
	4.2.1. The stages of development and characteristics relevant to the learning needs.	4,02	OK
	4.2.2. Social, cultural, religious and economic backgrounds relevant to the learning needs of students.	3,70	OK
	4.2.3. The potential, interests and learning methods of the student are relevant to the student's learning needs.	3,70	OK
	4.2.4. Characteristics and learning methods of disabled students	3,70	OK
	4.2.5. The diversity of learners' learning needs for inclusive learning.	4,19	OK
4.3	Curriculum and how to use it	4,11	OK
	4.3.1. Use of curriculum in a student-centric learning process.	3,99	OK
	4.3.2. Use of assessments to enhance participant-centred learning dictated measurements, calculators, and computer software.	4,10	OK
	4.3.3. Use of strategies to enhance student-centric learning	4,12	OK
	4.3.4. Use of effective learning strategies for access to literacy and numeration learning of students	4,24	OK
Average Competence Score		3,57	

II. Qualitative Data Findings

A. Findings about HCM System in SDIT Ar-Rahmah

The result of the interview reveals HCM system in SDIT Ar-Rahmah as outlined in Figure 4.1. In the figure, it is shown that HCM system in SDIT Ar-Rahmah consists of the following processes: 1) planning, 2) recruitment, 3) selection, 4) induction, 5) supervision & evaluation, 6) compensation and promotion. Further, the jobs the HCM system is distributed among several positions, including Finance & General Administration (GA) department, School Principal and Head of YP Ar-Rahmah. Also, there are three people who are directly in charge of the HCM process, including Head of YP Ar-Rahmah, School Principal of SDIT Ar-Rahmah and Administrative officer of SDIT Ar-Rahmah.

1) Planning

In the planning process, School Principal and Head of YP Ar-Rahmah will be regularly in contact about the condition of the school and the development progress of the goal. The planning process usually occur at the end of academic year. Currently, in the 2023-2024 Academic Year, SDIT Ar-Rahmah, supported by YP Ar-Rahmah, sets the goal of becoming a leading school in Asahan regency, North Sumatra. In achieving that, both School Principal and Head of YP Ar-Rahmah are responsible in ensuring that the employees recruited will be optimised to support the achievement of the goal. Currently, the school has reached the number of teachers planned to be recruited, which is a total of 12 teachers.

2) Recruitment

In the recruitment process, both School Principal and Head of YP Ar-Rahmah will work together to search for candidates. The search for candidates are not limited to their own networks, but extended to the networks of the teachers and members of YP Ar-Rahmah. However, both School Principal and Head of YP Ar-Rahmah are responsible for updating on the opening of recruitment and communicating it to the whole organization and beyond. Further, during this process, both School Principal and Head of YP Ar-Rahmah will be involved in the interview and testing process. Head of YP Ar-Rahmah is usually doing the initial interview to see whether the candidate will be a good fit to the organisation before reviewing their skills and competencies. While the School Principal, acts the “user” and is testing and interviewing more heavily on technical skills and competence.

3) Selection

Selection process will be done after thoroughly assessing the candidate and discussions between the School Principal and Head of YP Ar-Rahmah. In the selection process, Board of Directors (BoD) and Founders of YP Ar-Rahmah will be updated on the selection. On several occasions, the candidates will also be interviewed by one of the BoD members.

4) Induction

Induction is the first and the only training program available in SDIT Ar-Rahmah. The induction process differs among different new employees depending on their experience. Generally, all new teachers get information about the school and class management system. The training is given by the School Principal. Further, there is no specific training that is related to the teachers' skills or competence in the induction process. If a new teacher is less experienced, he or she will be paired with a teacher of the same level and be asked to assist the said teacher in class for a week. This is also where many knowledge transfers occur between existing teachers and new teachers. After a week of assistance, the new teacher will start to run their own class while supervised by a more senior teacher or by the School Principal. This will occur for a maximum of one month (probation period). After the probation period, the teacher will be expected to have settled in and run their own class. At the end of the probation period, the senior teacher and School Principal will give feedback on his or her performance and how they can improve.

5) Supervision & Evaluation

Supervision and evaluation is done solely by the School Principal. As for supervision, the School Principal oversees all teachers directly on all aspects of teaching including the teachers' roster and teaching schedules, classroom management, curriculum management. The role of the School Principal in the supervision process is more towards managing the operations and less about overseeing the performance of the teachers. There are no set of rules and guidance for evaluation. Evaluations are provided when necessary and usually in the form of warning. Nonetheless, at the end of the semester, the School Principal will evaluate on the graduates. They will then discuss on the strategy to improve on the outcomes together and implement the strategy on the following semester or academic year.

6) Compensation and Promotion

Compensation and promotion are the processes handled by Head of YP Ar-Rahmah. As the school is privately subsidised, compensation regulation mostly comes from the BoD members. The compensation process is not based on merit or performance, but rather on teacher’s attendance and needs. Teacher’s attendance will affect on their daily meal allowance. In terms of needs, teachers who are working at SDIT Ar-Rahmah will receive wage and benefits according to their family size and children education needs. Nonetheless, all wages received by SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers are still below the minimum wage band of the area although it is competitive compared with other private schools in the area. Further, promotions in SDIT Ar-Rahmah are also done according to the school’s needs rather than individual performance.

Figure 3. HCM System in SDIT Ar-Rahmah

B. Findings about Competency Development in SDIT Ar-Rahmah

SDIT Ar-Rahmah implemented several policies to improve its educational quality including 1) the improvements of supporting facilities and 2) improvement of teachers’ competencies. First, it aims to improve accreditation in order to get better recognition and gain more trust from the parents. Currently, the school is accredited C due its lack of facilitation in the previous building. Nonetheless, throughout 2022, the school has moved into a bigger building and built several facilities needed to improve accreditation. Several building improvements have been finished at the end of 2022/2023 academic year.

With regards to improving teachers’ competencies, SDIT Ar-Rahmah aims to have more teachers certified through the Program Pendidikan Guru certification (PPG). This aims to improve teachers’ competencies as well as their welfare through the government certification allowance program. When the teachers are certified, they will be well equipped with all the necessary competencies including personality competencies, pedagogical competencies, social competencies, and professional competencies. These improvements will greatly help teachers in managing their workload, teaching preparation as well as their ability in evaluating students and building more genuine interest and the students personal development. Moreover, the certification can also help improve school accreditation. Thus, this policy is targeted at improving teachers’ competencies and consequently educational quality provided by SDIT Ar-Rahmah. In addition to PPG certification, there are no competency development program that is being planned and implemented.

Finally, the current competency development program through PPG certification is deemed to be ineffective by the respondents, particularly the School Principal and the Head of YP Ar-Rahmah. The main reason is that many teachers in SDIT Ar-Rahmah are yet to be qualified to join the PPG certification program due to administrative issues, namely the length of teaching experience and lack of research paper to be submitted. More preparations need to be done to ensure more teachers can enrol to the PPG certification program. These preparations shall be managed by the school to ensure it effectively reaches the desired results.

III. Discussions

With regards to the human capital management system in SDIT Ar-Rahmah, there are several major components of an effective HCM system for elementary schools that is missing namely, Professional Development and Performance Management.

Odden (2011) maintains HCM framework for elementary schools that include four major elements that are: 1) talent acquisition, 2) talent development and motivation, 3) talent retention, 4) school leaders, with each elements containing certain components. Sukawati et al., (2020) also puts forward an effective HCM process on elementary schools based on numerous literature research. The process include: 1) job analysis, 2) employee selection, 3) orientation and placement, 4) training, 5) mutation, 6) promotion and 7) compensation. The two frameworks are adapted into a HCM System in Elementary Education as shown in Figure 4.2.

The current HCM system in SDIT Ar-Rahmah comprises of numerous components including 1) planning, 2) recruitment, 3) selection, 4) induction, 5) supervision & evaluation, 6) compensation and promotion. Analysed using the HCM in Education framework as posited by Odden (2011) and Sukawati et al. (2020), the system still lacks several major processes namely within the Talent Development and Motivation, particularly the Professional Development and Performance Management aspects. Clearly, the system still lacks Professional development component for it to be more effective. A professional development shall be focused on the specific needs of each teacher which will be apparent through their performance in collaborative work with colleagues, as well as the observed strength and weaknesses from performance evaluation (Odden, 2011, p.119). An evaluation prior to training or professional development is a prerequisite to an effective professional development effort. By understanding the individualised needs of each teacher, an effective method of training can be better designed (Sukawati et al., 2020). Also, through understanding the required competencies or learning materials, the raining can become more targeted to each individual teacher's weaknesses or need.

Moreover, performance management is a necessary process to ensure that the school achieve its main goals. This is typically accomplished by providing clear and attainable term goals for the employees, be it for the department, or individual goals. (Odden, 2011). Despite having an organizational goal, SDIT Ar-Rahmah lacks a structured and systematic performance management system from the elaboration of strategy and plan to achieve the goal. Indeed, a lack of clear and attainable goal as part of an employee's performance management might result in decreased motivation (Sukawati, 2020). Additionally, a performance management scheme usually includes monetary and/or non-monetary benefits to motivate employees. This can support employees in achieving their individual and department KPIs. However, it is important to note that for the performance management plan to run effectively, School Principal must maintain his role as evaluator and supervisor of the teacher, while leading and supporting the teachers' morale through his leadership. Thus, the role of School Principal is integral in the performance management process.

From human resource perspective, the organisation does not have a HCM department due to limited financial resources. Therefore, the jobs within the HCM system is distributed to three departments and roles, including: Finance and GA department, School Principal, Head of YP Ar-Rahmah. Strategic HCM functions that is related to teacher's competency development is solely handled by the School Principal. The School Principal is also expected to plan and organize teacher training and supervision. However, the School Principal falls shorts on delivering a strategic training program for teachers' development. According to the School Principal's testimony, the planning and implementation of school expansions that occurred throughout 2022/2023 AY takes a lot of time and effort, thus, his tasks were overloaded and did not have time to focus on planning internal competency development tasks (Z. Marpaung, personal communication, 16 July 2023). In addition, the position of Head of Finance and GA department has also been vacant since the beginning of 2022/2023 AY. Both the School Principal and the Head of YP Ar-Rahmah were not yet to find a qualified candidate to fill in the position. As a result, the existing competency development program is only focused on PPG certification. This is also due to encouragement from the Head of the Foundation and Trustees to increase the number of teachers taking certification to support the increase in school accreditation.

The series of occurrences that lead to the inability of the School Principal to plan and implement teachers competency development programs due to lack of manpower shows inefficiency in the workload management that results in lowered productivity of the School Principal. As the role of Head of Finance and GA is vacant, the School Principal was delegated the responsibility for Finance and GA tasks, including: 1) preparation of school administration work programs 2) administrative tasks related to school financial management, 3) administrative tasks related to staff and students, 4) preparation of equipment administration, 5) compilation and presentation of school data/statistics, 6) preparation of reports on the implementation of administrative management activities on a regular basis, 7) attend special meetings related to administrative matters. Further, it is also discovered that current Administrative Officer is inexperienced and unskilled in Finance and GA tasks, thus limiting her capability to basic administrative tasks, mainly for administrative tasks required by teachers and students, equipment-related tasks, managing IT system for school

rosters, financial management tasks and reporting. Thus, the lack of manpower hindered the School Principal from running his other main functions.

According to Odden (2011) school leaders are the “human capital managers” of the school HCM system who are responsible for the process of interview, selection, evaluation, feedback provision, coaching and overseeing other functions within the school (Odden, 2011, p.47). However, in facing the lack of manpower, the school leaders, namely the School Principal, was merely reacting to the situation and shows inability to assess the situation and manage the workforce effectively to find the best solution. In theory, the best practice of School Principal leadership is maintained as way or effort of the principal in influencing, encouraging, guiding, directing, and mobilizing teachers, staff, students, parents of students, and other related parties, to work/participate to achieve the goals set (Lubis & Haidir, 2019). Also, in the internal SDIT Ar-Rahmah document of Employees Job Description, the main function of a Scholl Principals is summarised as Educator, Manager, Administrator, Supervisor, Leader, Innovator dan Motivator or EMASLIM. In facing this issue, the School Principal are solely focused on his Administrator and Manager role, setting aside his other main functions and responsibilities. Instead of delegating his tasks to Vice Principal or other teachers, the School Principal took the responsibility all by himself. According to his testimony, the Vice Principal lacks to skill to handle matters related to Finance and GA tasks (Z. Marpaung, personal communication, 16 July, 2023). He also reflected on his choices and feels that the whole school function can benefit for trainings for specific skills that each individual need to make the organisation more effective. This indicates that inefficiency in carrying out the main functions of a School Principal. This could also be an indication of a lack of competency of the principal in carrying out its main function.

Figure 4. Human Capital Management in Education Adapted from Odden (2011) and Sukawati et al. (2020).

IV. Business Solutions

Based on the findings on the current competencies and HCM practices in SDIT Ar-Rahmah, appropriate activities and supporting tools for competency development can be formulated. The solution will be formulated using Lifelong Learning (LLL) approach to ensure continuity of competence improvements throughout the teachers’ employment. LLL approach is an appropriate method for developing teachers’ competence that requires continuous process. Indeed, teacher competence continuously evolves along with changes and necessitates teachers to constantly learn throughout their careers. The solution will be based the characteristics of Lifelong Learning as well as the system that allows for enablement of LLL implementation, which includes: 1) Formal and informal education, 2) Introspection and self-assessment, 3) Self-motivated learning, 4) Application of knowledge and skills, 5) Evaluation and improvement steps, and 6) Provision of facilities and tools that foster LLL habits.

1) Formal and informal education

Lifelong learning includes both formal education such as conventional schools, colleges, universities, and other higher educational establishments and culminates in certification, as well as informal education which may take place anywhere outside of the formal education institutions including at the workplace, home, communities and organization, and so on through peers, family members, coworkers, media, and more (Badyal et al., 2016, p.797; Laal, 2011, p.471). Currently, SDIT Ar-Rahmah’s approach for competency development is limited to trainings from PPG certification, which is a formal certification program held by Director General of Teachers and Education Personnel (Ditjen GTK). Nonetheless, the program is highly competitive and relatively difficult

to complete for SDIT Ar-Rahmah. Thus, it is recommended that the competency development program expands its training program by adding various informal training. The informal training program can include online and offline short courses at universities, training with teacher development organization such as Merdeka Mengajar platform from KemendikbudGuruBinar.id, short courses on specific competence via learning platforms (Coursera, Udemy and more), online and offline seminars, teachers' community discussions and more. Informal trainings can also occur within the organization through internal knowledge and best-practice sharing, book reviews, Islamic studies gathering (*pengajian*) and more.

These programs have the flexibility of selecting the specific competence or skills according to the teacher's needs, thus, making the learning process more applicative as the teacher can immediately apply the learning into their classroom. As analysed in the previous subchapter 4.1.1.3 on the results of the teachers competence survey, there are two areas of the teachers competence that falls below average, namely pedagogic and social competence. Pedagogic competences are essential in the learning process it measures how well teachers can maximize students' ability to actualize their abilities in class, as well as carry out assessment activities on the learning activities complete. Thus, this competency is essential in the development of student's capabilities and in the learning process. As for social competence, it is related to teacher's ability to communicate and engage effectively and efficiently with students, fellow teachers, students' parents/guardians, and the surrounding community. It affects not only the outcome of students, but also workplace effectiveness among colleagues. Thus, social competence is essential for increasing school's operations effectiveness. There is numerous informal training a teacher can receive to improve on their pedagogic and social competence. Thus, these two competences shall be prioritised in the design of learning materials, while also considering individual teacher's needs.

2) Introspection and self-assessment

Introspection and self-assessment are an essential part of LLL approach. One needs to understand their own competencies to determine their learning objectives. It is also important that the teacher reflect on their own strength and weaknesses (both with regards to their competence and their learning capabilities), identify their learning gaps and search for ways to improve their competencies (Pisklavkov, Rimal, & McGuirt, 2014, cited in Badyal et al., 2016, p.797). As an initial step, the evaluation of their competencies as surveyed in this paper can be utilised as a starting ground for assessment. Nonetheless, to build more reflective evaluation on oneself, the self-assessment and introspection can also be done after a teacher finishes a teaching day. Adopted from a self-assessment in Madania school as outlined by Musfah (2011, p.138), a teacher shall end their teaching day or week by answering the following questions to prompt on their self-reflection:

- How did the lesson go?
- How did the students behave?
- How was the student's understanding of the delivered material?
- What aspects of my teaching process today has been optimal?
- What aspects of my teaching process today requires improvements?
- What will I do to make my teaching better next time?
- How will I make the lesson different next time?

Teachers will answer these questions for students to get used to the practice of introspection and self-reflection in order to develop a better knowledge of themselves. Teachers may recognize their own teaching flaws and strengths. These inquiries, of course, are not restricted to the teaching process, but may also encompass other procedures connected to other teacher competences. Teachers, for example, might use comparable questions to reflect on performance in areas such as social competency, teacher/guardian participation, and community involvement in student learning processes.

3) Self-motivated learning

Self-motivated learning involves two important attributes, namely self-directed learning, and motivation. In self-directed learning, an individual does his or her own learning process at their own pace, while directed and supported by a trainer or instructor. Also, the material, source, and method of learning is flexible to the individual's interests and needs, thus, causing the motivation to learn to emerge (Hatton, 1997, cited in Musfah, 2011, p.117). Currently, the sentiment towards the PPG certification among SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers is rather negative as it is seen as a mere formality. Thus, it is important to provide numerous learning materials that offer wide variety of skills to help boost the teachers' success in the classroom. For instance, lessons on how to create a lesson plan, how to create worksheets and handouts, how to communicate to elementary school children, the psychology of elementary

students, writing skill, public speaking skills, understanding student's characters, and more. By providing freedom and flexibility to for them to choose the aspects of teaching that they are most interested in will help boost their motivation and ignite an excitement for learning. Teachers will experience practical and applicable lessons, which will be valuable for the learners (Musfan, 2011, p.131). Further, the learning materials can also include skills or topics that does not directly impact, but rather supplement the teaching skills and competence. This includes English lessons, computer lessons, Islamic and Quran studies, and more topics.

4) Application of knowledge and skills

A lesson and knowledge shall be put into application for it to translate to skills and competence. Indeed, to “understand” in requires the process of constructing knowledge through real experience. Understanding is not static, but constantly evolves and changes if learners construct new experiences that modify previous understandings. It requires a continuous learning process that is built through application and practice (Anggraena et al., 2022, p.44). As a consequence, teachers need to conduct their own experiential learning in which they apply their new knowledge. In applying lessons and knowledge, a teacher requires a degree of flexibility in their lesson plans and teaching methods. This is enabled by through the implementation of Kurikulum Merdeka in SDIT Ar-Rahmah. Kurikulum Merdeka provide flexibility to educational units and teachers to adapt, add to the wealth of subject matter, and align the curriculum with the characteristics of students, vision and mission of educational units, as well as culture and local wisdom (Anggraena et al., 2022, p.34).

5) Evaluation and improvement steps

Evaluation of the impact of training on competence can be done through teacher performance evaluation. Teacher performance appraisal can be carried out by the principal, himself, peers and by students, each with a different purpose. These four assessments can provide a comprehensive picture of a teacher's competence (Musfah, 2011, p.138). First, evaluation of teacher performance by the principal can be carried out by direct observation by the principal when the teacher teaches in class. This observation can be made three times to ensure consistency of assessment. The first observation was scheduled, and the second observation was carried out spontaneously without prior notification to the teacher concerned. The results of this assessment can assess the teacher's strengths and weaknesses, as well as what aspects need to be improved and are considered adequate. These findings can certainly help inform the training and learning needs of these teachers. Teacher evaluation can be carried out using the 2023 Teacher Competency Model by the Directorate General of GTK used in this study. However, it is highly recommended that the observation rubric be developed from this competency model and adapted to the service quality standards to be achieved by the school.

Second, peer assessments can focus on the social competence of teachers. Social competency according to the Teachers Competence Model 2023 by Ditjen GTK is shown in table 4.3, including collaboration with peers in improving learning processes (3.1), involving parents and community in learning processes (3.2) and engagement with peers and and broader networks of teachers' communities for improved learning. Peers can also assess teachers' social competencies that are not included in the Teachers Competence Model 2023 by the Directorate General of GTK, such as respect for others, client care orientation and teamwork and cooperation (Musfah, 2011, p.141). This assessment tends to look at the teacher's attitude, personality, and morals in getting along with the school community. Third, student assessment is intended to evaluate the teaching and learning process. Of course, this assessment could be given more accurately by students at higher levels such as grades 4-6. So, to add input from the student's side, an evaluation can also be carried out on the parents of students by asking about the impact of learning that parents observe at home. This of course can be a valuable input for teachers.

6) Provision of facilities and learning sources that foster LLL habits

Finally, to support the learning process of teachers requires the provision or certain facilities and learning sources. It will require basic facilities such as computer and internet connection. Learning sources such as books and learning materials shall also be provided, including access to online classes and webinars, subscription to learning materials, library membership and more. The school management might also need to collaborate with external parties to support learning. A lot of learning materials will require the support of instructor or experts, thus requiring the school to work with external parties. As a consequence, it requires proactivity from the school management to continuously collect and update learning sources, while collaborating with external parties to find efficient ways to hold competency development programs.

V. Implementation Plan

To do so, a new team shall be formed to initiate and implement the above competency development programs. Nonetheless, as the current organisation human resources are limited, it is suggested that a cross-functional team is formed among the teachers to accomplish this task. Cross-functional team is made up of employees from the same hierarchical level with different work areas to work together and accomplish a certain objective (Judge & Robbins, 2017, p.354). According to Judge and Robbins (2017, p.354), a cross-functional team is an effective way to allow people within the organisation to build new ideas, solve problems, and coordinate on complex projects. The collaborative efforts of individuals with different skills and strengths is one of its main benefits, especially for accomplishing a difficult task. The main task of the team is to build and lead change towards Lifelong Learning among SDIT Ar-Rahmah teachers through implementing the competency development program outlined. The tasks include, but are not limited to: researching and developing learning materials, collaborating with external parties for formal and nonformal trainings, develop teachers competence model that is in accordance to the school quality standards and objectives, develop evaluation forms, create regular learning/training schedule, check in with colleagues on their training needs and progress, collaborate with School Principal and Head of YP Ar-Rahmah for running and implementing the competency development program.

CONCLUSION

The Teacher Competence Survey evaluates four areas of competence for teachers at SDIT Ar-Rahmah: Pedagogic, Personal, Social, and Professional. The overall average competence score is 3.57 out of 5, with strengths in Professional and Personal competence and areas for improvement in Pedagogic and Social competence. The Human Capital Management (HCM) system at SDIT Ar-Rahmah involves various processes but lacks Professional Development and Performance Management for teachers. It is also discovered that the HCM system is highly reliant on the School Principal. Yet, there are several main functions related to Professional Development and Performance Management that the School Principal falls short in maintaining. To improve educational quality, SDIT Ar-Rahmah has implemented several policies, including improvements in supporting facilities and enhancing teachers' competencies through Program Pendidikan Guru (PPG) certification, which are faced with the issue of lack of ICT skills among some teachers, difficulties in passing the assessments and some teachers not fully understanding the benefits of additional certifications. Outside of the PPG certification, there are currently no competency development program being held or planned internally.

Improving educational quality requires addressing challenges in the HCM system and competency development programs. The proposed solution is a Lifelong Learning (LLL) approach, which is the suitable approach to ensure continuous improvement for teachers. The plan consists of six key elements: formal and informal education, introspection and self-assessment, self-motivated learning, application of knowledge and skills, evaluation and improvement steps and provision of facilities and tools for fostering LLL habits. The proposed solution suggests expanding the training program by incorporating informal trainings, encouraging introspection and self-assessment, providing flexibility for self-motivated learning, and emphasizing the application of knowledge through experiential learning. Evaluation through teacher performance assessments by School Principal, peers and students is proposed to assess the program's impact. Finally, it highlights the important of providing necessary facilities and resources to support teachers' learning. To implement the plan effectively, a cross-functional team is proposed to be formed among teachers to lead and initiate the competency development programs. The implementation plan includes various stages such as socialisation, strategy design, resource provision, training and evaluation, and continuous improvement based on assessment results. Overall, the goal is to create a conducive learning environment and culture of continuous improvement, enhancing the competencies of SDIT Ar-Rahmah's teachers through lifelong learning.

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